

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series
Vol.XVI.Book.I-IV

January - December 2024

किरणावली
Sanskrit Research Foundation
Thiruvananthapuram

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series

Vol.XVI. Book. I-IV

January-December

2024

Sanskrit Research Foundation

T.C 39/37

Thiruvananthapuram-36

KIRANĀVALĪ

ISSN 0975-4067

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14576256>

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

A Peer-Reviewed Research Journal

Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohan (Rtd)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohan@gmail.com

Executive Editor

Prof. Dr.C.S.Sasikumar (Rtd.)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.sasikumarcs@gmail.com

Managing Editor

Prof. Dr.G.Narayanan

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.g.narayanan@gmail.com

Editorial board

Dr.V.Sisupalapanikkar, Professor of Sanskrit(Rtd.) Uty. of Kerala

Dr.K.Muthulakshmi, Professor of Vedanta, S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.R.Vijayakumar, Professor of Vyakarana(Rtd.), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.P.Chithambaran, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd),S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.P.K.Dharmarajan, Professor of Sahitya, (Rtd) S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.K.K.Sundaresan, Associate Professor in Vedanta, SSUS.Kalady

Dr.S.Sobhana, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.T.Devarajan, Professor of Sanskrit (Rtd), University of Kerala

Associate Editor

Dr.R.Jinu

Associate Professor, Dept of English,

Noorul Islam Centre For Higher Education, Kumaracoil,

Thuckalay, Kanyakumari, Tamil Nadu

jichelnu@gmail.com

Contents

Editors Note	5
Fractions or kalāsavarṇa - Concepts in the Gaṇitasārasaṅgraha (G.S.S) of Mahāvira	Dr. P.M.Mini 7
Vrikshayurveda Literature- A Review	Dr. K.Murali 12
Existence Of Mind and its Function: Śrī Śankara's Perspective	Dr. V Vasanthakumari 23
Regional Peculiarities in Prakriyāsarvasva	Dr. Yamuna.K 30
Parāstotra - Edition and Study	Dr. J.P. Prajith 37
Alienation through Exile: A Critical Introspection into John Dos Passos' Nineteen Nineteen	Dr. Sanil T. Sunny 44
The Evolution of Indian Sculptural Art: Interaction with Western Styles and Development of Modernism	Dr. T.G Jyothilal 49
Scope of Sanskrit Studies in the Kerala Context	Dr.Shylaja S 55
Desamangalam Srikantha Variar - A Versatile Scholar	Dr.V.P.Udayakumar 67
A Comprehensive Review of Adharaneeya and Dharaneeya Vega	Dr. H.A.Anu, Dr. Haritha Chandran, Dr. Haroon Irshad, Dr. Leena P.Nair 72
A Significant Emphasis on Charakokta Chaturvidha Pariksha	Dr.Kesavan.V G, Dr.Haroon Irshad, Dr.Leena P.Nair, Dr. Haritha Chandran 84
Concept Of Manas- A Glimpse from Yoga Darsana	Dr. Anu Gopal, Dr. Haritha Chandran, Dr. Leena P Nair, Dr. Haroon Irshad 96
Women Life in Royal Harem- A Study Based on Nāṭyaśāstra And Mālavikāgnimitra	Dr. Ajitha T S 106
Effective Strategies For Implementing The Integrated Teacher Education Programme Under NEP- 2020	Prof. K.K. Harshkumar, Dr. Anand Rautmale 113
“Pancha Mahabhuta in Ayurveda: Understanding and Practical Applications”	Dr. Aswiny Sreekumar.T 121
“Dynamic Portrayals of Women in Amarushatak: Unravelling Love, Creation, Destruction, Submission, and Dominance”	Dr. Preeti R. Pujara 135
Literary Representation of the Ashtamudi Lake sketched through Poetic Imagery: An Exploration based on Selected Poems in Malayalam	Jayalekshmi J 145
Reviving Classical Narratives: Exploring the Cultural, Linguistic, and Literary Significance of Sanskrit Literature in Contemporary Contexts	Dr. Yeshpal, 155
Vedic Thought on Nakshatra Science	Dr. Kanta 172
Vedāntic Reflections in Kālidāsa's Literature: A Journey through Ancient Wisdom	Dr. K. K. Abdul Majeed 179
The Transformative Power of Yogic Meditation: Insights from the Isha Upanishad	Dev Prakash Gujela , Neha Gujela 188
Sanskrit: The Language of Innovation in Ancient Indian Knowledge Systems.	Abdul Rasheed K. 197
The Role of Vedānta as a Mediator between Science and Religion	Dr. Abdulla Sha R., Dr. Midhun P., 207

Concept of Guṇa in Bhagavad Gīta	Dr. Shyji K.K.	212
Pancatantram's perspective of accepting an 'hors de combat'. Kasthuri P. K.		217
Integral Yoga of Sri Aurobindo	Remya.S	223
The Historical Aspects Of 'Translation' (Anuvādam) - An Overview	Dr. Sajeesh C S	227
The Malayali Diaspora in the US: A close reading of Mira Jacob	Nirupama Suneetha	235
From Elancon To Kollam: The Transformation of A Port Cty	Gowri S Panicker	242
Influence of Nārayanīya on Kṛṣṇagīti	Dr Jayanisha K	255
Subverting Ableist Binaries: An Analysis of the Confluence of Disability Studies and Blue Humanities in Toni Crowther's From Wheelchair to Water	Sneha Jacob	263
Connecting the Concept of 'Avatar' to the Concept of Consciousness in Upanishads	Venugopalan P.M	269
Extraction of historicity from Sanskrit literature	Soorya A.P	281
चिन्सुखेन प्रतिपादितं अविद्यालक्षणम्	डॉ. सन्तोष सि. आर्	285
सामाजिकसमस्यापरिहारे भरतीयज्ञानपरम्परान्तर्गतस्य योगशास्त्रस्य स्थानम्	डा. श्रीजित् टि.जि	289
पतञ्जलिकालीनः लोकव्यवहारः-महाभाष्याधारेण एकमनुशीलनम्	डा.रूपा. वि	293
मानवीयमूल्यबोधोत्तरणे मूच्छकटिकम्	ड.मृत्युञ्जयमण्डलः परेशकैवर्त्यः	299
रघुवंशमहाकाव्ये रसतत्त्वसमीक्षणम्	काञ्चनवारिकः	304
नारीचैतन्योद्बोधे शङ्खनादः	डॉ टुम्पा जाना	308
आधुनिकसंस्कृतसाहित्ये गलज्जलिकायाः वैशिष्ट्यम्	सतीश चन्द्र दास	313
श्रीमच्छंकराचार्यकृतच्छान्दोग्योपनिषद्भाष्यस्य कतिपयशब्दवाक्यानां रूपवाक्यशब्दार्थतत्त्वनिरूपणम्	रणिता घोष	321
सदाचारो वेदाश्च ।	डा.अशोक कुमार एन्.के.	327
साम्प्रतिकसन्दर्भे अपरिग्रहः	डॉ. शुभमयपाहाडी	331
मनुसंहिता : 'ब्रह्मतत्त्व' विषयकम् एकं संक्षिप्तं मतम्	अमल कुमार कर	335
श्रीकाशीमठाधीशानां श्रीमत्सुधीन्द्रतीर्थानां स्तोत्रेषु छन्दांसि तथा सौन्दर्यम्	दिव्यश्री जगदीश पै बि. , & भास्कर वि भट्टः	339
सिद्धान्तग्रन्थेषु ब्राह्मणमानम्	डा. राघवेंद्रः	347
एतत्संज्ञेत्यत्र कः समासः	डा. गोपालकृष्णन् रघुः	352
मेघदूतस्य सांस्कृतिकमीमांसा	डा. सत्येन्दु शर्मा	356
जान्-म्यूर-प्रणीतस्य 'श्रीपौलचरित्रम्' इति महाकाव्यस्य संस्कृतालङ्कारशास्त्रदृष्ट्या समीक्षामिका विमृष्टिः	डा. सौम्यजित् सेनः	360
आधुनिकयुगे संस्कृतशिक्षा प्रसारार्थं विद्यासागरस्यावदानम्	डः तानिया-सिकदारः	369
तद्धितप्रत्ययेषु इत्संज्ञकवर्णाः ।	आतिरा. जि	372
अद्वैतसिद्धेः मङ्गलश्लोकस्य अप्रामाण्यशङ्कावारणम्	कार्तिक शर्मा के , ड. हरिकृष्ण शर्मा के.एन्	376
न्यायव्याकरणतन्त्रानुसंधे पदस्वरूपविवेचनम्	प्रणबेष् भट्टाचार्यः	381
पीयूषवर्षश्रीजयदेवाचार्य-श्रीकेशविमिश्रयोः मते शान्तरसविमर्शः	सत्येनशीटः	387
आलंकारिकदण्डिस्वीकृतः शब्दालङ्कारप्रपञ्चः	डॉ. शुभ्रजित् सेनः	393
लिधा एव पदशब्दस्य प्रवृत्तिः	डा. सुदीप-मण्डलः	400
About the journal		407

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14642253>

Concept of Manas- A Glimpse from Yoga Darsana

Dr. Anu Gopal¹,

Dr. Haritha Chandran², Dr. Leena P Nair³, Dr. Haroon Irshad⁴

Abstract

The main aim of Ayurveda is maintaining the health of healthy person and to cure the diseases of a diseased person. Yoga Darsana is primarily concerned with the nature of the mind, the means to attain self-realization, and the path to liberation. *Manas Siddhanta* has been clearly portrayed by both *Astika* and *Nastika* philosophers. Yoga-Darshana, one of the six *Astika Darshana*, is solely devoted to *Manas*. Ayurveda and Yoga Darshana has lots of similarities in their basic principles. Both are inter-related science and have accepted basic principles like *Manas*, *Atma*, *Panchamahabhoota* etc. *Manas* and *Citta* are the two terms used in Yoga Sutra, with almost similar sense as *Sattva*. *Citta* has various states of existence, according to the Yoga Sutra, ranging from the extremely agitated condition of *Kshipta* to the supreme peaceful state of *Samadhi*. The functions of *Citta* including *Pramana*, *Viparyaya* etc helps to understand the existence of *Cittavritti*. Yoga is characterised as

1 Final year P.G scholar, Department of Moulika Siddhanta (Basic Principles of Ayurveda) , Amrita School of Ayurveda, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, Amritapuri, India

Co-Authors

- 2 Assistant Professor, Department of Moulika Siddhanta (Basic Principles of Ayurveda) , Amrita School of Ayurveda, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, Amritapuri, India
- 3 Associate Professor, Department of Moulika Siddhanta (Basic Principles of Ayurveda) , Amrita School of Ayurveda, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, Amritapuri, India
- 4 Associate Professor, Department of Moulika Siddhanta (Basic Principles of Ayurveda) , Amrita School of Ayurveda, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, Amritapuri, India

the control of mental activity. Yoga helps to bring one out of the *Panchaklesha* caused mainly due to ignorance (*Avidya*). The ability to control one's thoughts is necessary for self-realization. By this it becomes imperative to understand the concept of *manas* from Yoga darshana.

Introduction

Yoga Darsana, often referred to simply as Yoga, is a classical philosophical system that originated in ancient India. It is one of the six orthodox schools of Indian philosophy and was expounded by the sage Patanjali in his text called the Yoga sutras. Yoga Darsana is primarily concerned with the nature of the mind, the means to attain self-realization and the path to liberation.

Manas Siddhanta has been clearly portrayed by philosophers both *Astika and Nastika*. Yoga-Darshana, one of the six *Astika Darshana*, is solely devoted to *Manas*. In the first chapter of his book, Yoga-Sutra, Maharshi Patanjali defined yoga in relation to *citta* and substituted the word *citta* for *manas*. The Yoga Sutra provides a detailed explanation of *Citta Vritti* (mental functions), *Cittabhumi* (mental planes), *Pancaklesha* (five emotional states), and many more concepts that are closely related to various mental states.

Materials and Methods

Extensive literary search done on the related topics from Yoga Darsana, Charaka samhita and articles from data bases like Pubmed, google scholar etc.

Ashtanga Yoga

The word "Yoga" itself means union or connection. In the context of Yoga Darsana, it refers to the union of the individual self (*jivatman*) with the Universal consciousness (*Brahman*). Yoga is seen as a practical discipline that encompasses various practices and techniques to achieve this union. These practices include physical postures (*asanas*), breath control (*pranayama*), meditation (*dhyana*), ethical principles (*yamas and niyamas*) and more.

The Yoga Sutras of Patanjali describes the eight fold path of Yoga, known as Ashtanga Yoga or Raja Yoga, which provides a comprehensive framework for spiritual development. The eight limbs are (YS 2/29):

1. *Yama*: Ethical rules or restrictions, such as honesty, non-violence, and lack of possessiveness.
2. *Niyama*: Moral standards or virtues like orderliness, contentment, and self-control.
3. *Asana*: Physical postures used to build flexibility, strength, and balance.
4. *Pranayama*: Breathing exercises that control and broaden the prana.
5. *Pratyāhara*: Withdrawal of the senses from external stimulation and development of inner awareness.
6. *Dhaarana*: Mental concentration.
7. *Dhyaana*: The unbroken flow of awareness towards the focus during meditation.
8. *Samaadhi*: Union with the object of meditation while in a blissful, total state of absorption.

Pancha kosha in yoga

In Yoga Darsana the mind is regarded as one among the five koshas that surround the true self. They are as follows:

1. *Annamaya kosha*: The body or its outer covering.
2. *Pranamaya kosha*- the life force or the breath.
3. *Manomaya kosha*- the mind or mental sheath.
4. *Vijnanamaya kosha*- the intellect or wisdom sheath.
5. *Anandamaya kosha*- the bliss sheath or the state of pure happiness.

The *manomaya kosha*, or the mental sheath, represents the mind, thoughts, emotions and sensory experiences. It is through the practice of yoga that one seeks to calm and control the fluctuations of the mind to attain higher states of consciousness and self-realization.

Manas and chitta according to yoga sutra

Manas and Chitta are the two terms used in Yoga Sutra, with almost similar sense as *Satva*. *Manas* is nonself-illuminative and is exposed through *Purusha* (soul). According to Yoga Sutra, *Chitta* is the first product of *Prakriti*, comprising *Buddhi* (intellect), *Ahankara* (self-conscious) and *Manas*. Here, *Manas*, *Buddhi*, and *Ahamkara* all are together known as *Citta* (YS1/2). In Charaka Samhita

Sharira Sthana, all these three are differently explained. *Hrudaya* is considered as the sthana of *manas* as per Charaka Samhitha.

In Yoga Sutra, the word *Chitta* is explained as the concentration on sensory objects such as smell, taste, touch, colour, or sound which helps to stabilize its fluctuations. It shows that *Manas* is fluctuating in nature and that it has an ability to concentrate. *Chitta* is explained as very bright and pure by nature, but its brightness is often masked by in born psychological *Klesha* (disorders). *Chitta* has various states of existence, according to the Yoga Sutra, ranging from the extremely agitated condition of *Kshipta* to the supreme peaceful state of *Samadhi*. *Manas* is a word that is frequently used to describe all these diverse *Chitta* status.

Manasika bhavas (states of mind):

Bhagavan Vyasa outlines five states of *Manas* in his commentary on the Yoga Sutra:

- ***Kshipta*** - *Manas* is tempted to focus on the sensory object when it is awake. The natural energy compels it to go out through the sensory faculties. Since the mind constantly switches their focus from one thing to another, it is incapable of managing itself. The driving force at this point is purely interest with the object. *Kshipta* is the name of this state.
- ***Vikshipta*** - This stage occurs when the *manas* is unable to concentrate on an object, and is wandering around e.g. while reading a book or watching any object the *Manas* will pass through a series of information. This state is called *Vikshipta*. ***Mudha*** - *Mudha* is a state of mind that is dull or lethargic. *Manas* is not learning anything new at this point.
- ***Ekagrata***- *Manas* focusses itself on a specific thought or subject during this stage. *Manas* when committed to an idea won't change much that often. In this stage, *Manas* remains focused on a single object without any distraction.
- ***Niruddha*** - It is the situation in which *Manas* is in control and cannot be deterred. Yogi can reach the spiritual level in this situation. It is the thoughtless state where *Manas* can function without distract. Typically, everyone aspires to own a variety of goods. One becomes dissatisfied when one yearns for more.

Frustration leads to miseries. There should not be any desires to attain happiness. The *Citta* can be made peaceful by letting up of desires. In this condition, known as *Niruddha Manas*, craving for the fulfilment of wishes ends.

Classification of mental functions

Patanjali has classified the mental functions into five categories:

1. *Pramana*, 2. *Viparyaya* 3. *Vikalpa* 4. *Nidra* and 5. *Smriti* (YS 1/6)
1. *Pramana*: *Pramanas* are the means to attain the valid knowledge in the presence of *manas*. They include *Pratyaksham*(direct perception), *Anumanam* (inference), *Agama*(authentic testimony). Direct perception is obtaining knowledge through sense faculties. The validity of the knowledge thus obtained is confirmed using the other two- the *Anumana* and *Agama*. There are many instances where one may not perceive things directly. In such places inference is used. Where perception and inference fails one have to depend on Authentic testimony.
2. *Viparyaya (illusion)*: Illusion is the misperception like a rope is mistaken for a snake. Defective sense faculty, lack of optimal conditions for functioning of the faculty and defective reasoning generate invalid knowledge.
3. *Vikalpa (imagination)*: Here there will be verbal expression of things but there won't be any such existence in reality.
4. *Nidra (sleep)* : During *nidra* one may recollect the length and depth of sleep and dreams. This indicates that there were mental activities during the sleep. Hence dreamful sleep is also called as a mental activity.
5. *Smriti (memory)*: Memory is the ability to recall previously stored events. *Nidra*, *Pramana*, *Viparyaya*, and *Vikalpa* serve as intermediaries to help people recollect information that has already been stored. Thoughts are produced as a stimulus within the *Chitta* itself. This further prompts the memory of the previous deed.

Panchaklesha according to patanjali

On many occasions, *Manas* cause unfavourable feelings. A person who is emotionally disturbed may act inappropriately, talk foolishly or think foolishly. Person becomes uncontrollable in his

actions. This is due to *Avidya* (ignorance), *Asmita* (egoism), *Raga* (attachment), *Dvesha* (aversion), and *Abhinivesha* (*YS 2/3*) (desire for life), which is collectively called as '*Panchaklesha*' according to Patanjali. Numerous psychosomatic illnesses are brought on by *avidya*. Erasing ignorance ought to be the first step to be followed. The remaining four are caused as a result of *Avidya*. Every action a person takes is aimed at bringing them enjoyment. The *Chitta* believes that happiness is found in the things we can see and touch. When these desired items are not granted, the person becomes emotionally upset.

Yoga is characterised as the control of mental activity. The ability to control one's thoughts is necessary for self-realization. Self is real knowledge and is free from suffering. When *Chitta vritti* is active, the true self is hidden. The bottom of the pond can be seen through the clear water once the waves have subsided. *Manas* is rarely calm at any given time. *Citta* continues to work even during sleep. It is therefore quite challenging to develop mental discipline. Once *Citta Vritti* has subsided, *Citta* feels like its true self. *Manas* is in a pleasant condition at this time. A person begins to develop an aversion to exterior sense items once they become aware of this truth. This is referred to as renunciation or *vairagya*. According to yoga, one can stop mental functions by *Vairagya* (renunciation) and *Abhyasa* (practise). The purpose of Astanga Yoga-Yama's first posture is to develop a renunciative mindset.

Manas moves at a rate that makes it impossible to determine the order of transactions. In Ayurveda the qualities possessed by mind is regarded as *Anutvam and Ekatvam*. *Anutvam* indicates the minuteness of mind while *Ekatvam* shows the speed of perception, which makes us feel a series of happening occurring all together at a single moment.

The mental operations can be categorised as *Jnana Pradhana* (cognitive functions), *Bhavana Pradhana* (affective functions), and *Ceshta Pradhana* (conative functions). Again there are two different sorts of cognitive processes: *Yatharthanubhava* (genuine knowledge) and *Ayatharthanubhava* (false knowledge).

Obstacles of knowledge in yoga:

The *Bhavana* (affective) is then classified into nine types, which are destructive in nature and are called *Citta Vikshepa* or mental distractions- *Vyadhi* (morbidness), *Styana* (debility), *Samshaya* (doubt), *Pramada* (inadvertence), *Alasya* (sloth), *Avirati* (sensuality), *Bhranti Darshana* (wrong understanding), *Alabdha Bhūmikatva* (nonattainment of plan), and *Anavasthitatva* (YS 1/30) (instability).

Every action a person takes is aimed at acquiring happiness. Yoga teaches that happiness is within us. Once *Citta Vritti* is resolved, the *Citta* experiences the natural self, which is a blissful state of *Manas*. The ignorant *Citta* believes that the happiness is in the external sensory objects. This tempts the *Citta* to attach with these objects. When these desired objects are denied, the person gets irritated and becomes emotionally disturbed.

Discussion

The Yoga Darshana is the only one among the six *Astika Darshanas* to fully define the idea of *Manas*. *Manas* can be regarded to be the focal point of the entire Yoga Darshana. The Patanjala Yoga Darshana provides a comprehensive explanation of *Manas*. *Pratyahara*, *Dharana*, *Dhyana*, and *Samadhi* are some of the *Antaranga Yoga* practises that can be used to understand the absolute form of *Manovijnana* and *Cetana*. The minute status of *Sukshma Sharira* can be understood through yoga sadhana. In very first Sutra of Yoga Darshana, Maharshi Patanjali defined Yoga as a method to control *Citta Vritti* where *Citta* can be understood as *Manas*.

The teachings of Maharshi Patanjali are regarded as the base of Raja Yoga. Raja Yoga deals with the process of restraining the *Sattva*. Maharshi Patanjali provides comprehensive explanations of the nature, stages, functions, diseases, and control strategies of *manas*. One of the most original works on psychology is the Yoga Sutra. In the Yoga Sutra, Maharshi Patanjali referred to *Dhyana* as “*Tatrapratyekanata Dhyanam* (YS 3/2).” *Pratyaya* refers to *Karana*, the root cause. *Ektanata* refers to the movement of related *Citta Vritti*. *Citta Vritti* that focuses on just one aspect of a subject is referred to as *Dhyana*, while that which is equivalent to *manas* is

referred to as *Dhyeya*.

Yoga Shastra deals more with health giving aspect of *Manas*. The most sophisticated science that highlights the neurological, psychological, and etiological aspects of *Manas* is yoga. Yoga also demonstrates several ways to maintain the *Manas* in a healthy state and to address the typical imbalances that lead to psychosomatic diseases. Yogic Kriya can be helpful in controlling negative ideas, which may eventually lead to *Manas* being in a regulated state. The various normal and abnormal states of *Manas* can be used to explain the five *Citta Bhumi* of the Yoga Darshana. This *CittaBhumi* concept is easily interpreted in terms of various personality and psychological illnesses. Additionally, the Yoga Darshana describes the five *Klesha*, which are the different emotional aspects of *manas*.

Yoga Darshana, which is a science for managing the *Citta*, identified two methods—*Abhyasa and Vairagya*—for improving psychological hygiene. Various conducts are theorised there over and are known as Astanga Yoga in order to counteract the prevalent materialistic mentality and to accomplish upliftment towards spiritual advancement. *Tattva Smriti* and *Satyabuddhi*, which are described as the means and the way to *Moksha*, are mentioned by Caraka in a brief but significant manner under the heading “*Tattva Smriti and Satyabuddhi*”. *Achara Rasayana and Sadvritta* can be related to the *Yama, Niyama*, and other rules in Yoga sastra.

Between Yoga and Samkhya Darshana, there is some disagreement concerning where *Mana* originated. Although it is *Akriyashila, Atma is Jna, Vibuddha, and Karta*. It involves *Manas* to carry out its task. Here, the *Atma* is solely explained in terms of the *Jivatma* (which is connected to *Mana and Shaarira*), not the *Paramatma (Nirvikara)*.

Psychotherapeutic perspective of manas in ayurveda:

In Ayurveda, “*Manastatvam*” refers to the mental and emotional well-being of an individual. Ayurveda recognizes the importance of mental health in maintaining overall balance and harmony in the body. It views mind as an integral part of the human system and acknowledges its influence on physical health.

According to Ayurveda, the mind is composed of three subtle

energies or “*Gunas*” known as *Sattva*, *Rajas* and *Tamas*. As per Yoga darsana, *Sattva* represents all that is pure, ideal and tranquil. *Rajas* expresses itself in action, motion and violence. *Tamas* is the principle of solidity, immobile resistance and inertia. The interplay of these *Gunas* within the mind determines one’s mental state and overall well-being.

Acharya Charaka has given definition of *Satwavajaya Chikitsa* as “*Ahitebhyo Arthebhyo Manonigraha*” i.e. *Nigraha* from *Ahita Vishaya* is *Satwavajaya Chikitsa* for *Manasika Rogas* like *Unmada*, *Apasmara* etc. in the same way as described in definition of Yoga as “*Yogashcittavritti Nirodhah*”. i.e. *Nirodha* of *Chittavrittis* is *Yogasiddhi*.

Both Ayurveda and the modern perspective agree that various mental states, such as *chinta*, *shoka*, *kama*, *krodha* etc. can contribute to or act as *Hetu* for diseases. Therefore, there exists a connection between these *manasika bhavas* and the onset of *Sareerika vyadhi utpatti*. Ayurveda recognised this relationship thousands of years ago, as evident in the statement by Acharyas that “the *sareera* is interconnected with the *manas*, and the *manas* is interconnected with the *sareera*.” Consequently, mental states can serve as causes for physical diseases. The Acharyas also explained how different mental states can lead to imbalances in the bodily doshas such as *Kamashokabhayadvayu*, *Krodhatpittam*, *Trayomala*”. The body’s immunity always plays a crucial role in defending against various diseases, serving as the first line of defence to protect the body. The occurrence of any diseases can be an indication of the failure of the immune response. Different emotional behaviours (*Manasika bhavas*) thus disrupt the body’s immune system and contribute to the development of diseases.

The statement “*Rogasarve api mande agnau*” suggests that all diseases have impaired digestion- *Mandagni* as a common factor. Similarly, mental states also contribute to diseases through the same factor. When emotions such as *Krodha*, *Bhaya*, *Harsha*, *Chinta* etc. trigger the body’s “fight or flight and fright response”, the brain

shunts the blood flow away from the digestive system towards the muscles, preparing for physical exertion. As a result, inadequate blood supply to the gut leads to indigestion, which ultimately paves the way for disease.

Conclusion:

The ultimate aim of Ayurveda is *Purushartha prapti*, i.e. *Moksha prapti*. Acharya Charaka says that “*Yogo moksha Pravartaka*”. It means Yoga is one of the important Marga for *Moksha Prapti*. Although the concept of *Manas* has been fully explained by all schools of Indian philosophy, Yoga Darshana possesses the greatest number of aphorisms regarding *manas*. Yoga Darshana is developed for controlling the *Manas*, i.e. *Citta Vritti Nirodha* and through the *Abhyasa and Vairagya* one can achieve the goal of *Moksha*.

Works Cited

- Charaka. Caraka Samhita Sutrasthana. Edited by Dr. Tewari , Varanasi, Chaukhambha Vishvabharati, 2016.
- Charaka, and Chakrapani. Charaka Samhita (Charak Samhita with Ayurved Dipika Tika of Chakrapani. Varanasi, Chaukhambha Vishvabharati, 2017.
- Prabhavananda. Patanjali Yoga Sutras. Madras, India, Sri Ramakrishna Math, 2006.
- Suśruta. The Suśruta-Samhitá. Edited by P.V Sharma , Choukhambha Visvabharati, 2022.

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series Vol. XVI. Book I-IV

January - December 2024

ISSN 0975-4067

Printed and published by: Dr.C.S.Sasikumar, Secretary, Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram, for Sanskrit Research Foundation,